

PRIORITIZATION, COLLECTION, CONSERVATION AND USES OF CROP WILD RELATIVES IN INDIA

¹Ahlawat Sudhir Pal, ²K Pradheep, ³Singh Praveen Kumar

¹ICAR-National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, New Delhi-110 012, India, ²ICAR-National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, Regional Station, Thrissur, Kerala, India

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14016674>

Abstract. Importance of Crop Wild Relatives (CWR) as source of novel genes specifically for biotic and abiotic stress tolerance in context of climate change has increasingly been recognized at global level. However, a substantial number of wild species are facing threat, before their diversity is adequately explored and conserved. In-situ assessment of CWR resources to identify, rare, endangered or threatened species, is crucial for their protection, adaptation and evolution. Information on distribution, ecogeography, genetic worth, methodologies of identification, collection, conservation and utilization of CWR of Indian Gene Centre are scanty. Total 861 Indian CWR taxa (769 species) have been identified based on their closeness with crop as well as their potential use in 171 ICAR-mandated crops. Shortlisted taxa were further prioritized based on their economic importance, closeness to crop (GP-GP3), possession of traits of breeders' interest, extent of distribution and level of threat. Accordingly, 292 taxa (257 species) belonging to 85 crops are narrowed down. These high-priority taxa were analysed for gaps in collection and conservation. Of 292 taxa, only 167 were conserved in the National Genebank. While 28 taxa were represented with <5 accessions and 81 with <10 accessions, only 40 were with a fair number of accessions (≥ 50); however, they too lack representative samples from across geographical and ecological range. Fragile ecosystems - coastal and cold-arid ecosystem, and protected areas are priority targets for collection. The collection of CWR has significantly increased in past decade (7-8%). However, locating their habitat and species, asynchronous maturity, less seeds, problems in multiplication and evaluation for traits of interest are major constraints.

Keywords: crop wild relatives, conservation, germplasm, gap analysis, genebank, uses.

Major use of CWR is in breeding for biotic stress (diseases and pest resistance), followed by abiotic stress (drought, heat, frost, salinity, and submergence tolerance), agronomic and quality traits (e.g., nutrients, seed size, yield). Among crops, different species of CWR were used in breeding and improvement of wheat, rice, pigeonpea, greengram, blackgram (*Vigna* spp.), okra, chili, bittergourd, cucurbits (*Cucumis* spp.), and tomato etc. *Allium stracheyi*, *Brassica tournefortii*, *Cucumis melo* var. *alwarensis* and *Momordica muricata* are being cultivated as crop. Further, some of the wild relatives found in India are being used, and have potential as root-stock in fruits and vegetable crops like apple (*Malus baccata*), pear (*Pyrus pashia*), prunus (*P. mira*), Citrus (*C. jambhiri*) and Solanum (*S. torvum*, *S. nigrum*, *S. violaceum*), grapes (*Vitis lanata*, *Vitis palmata*), Kiwi (*Actinidia callosa*, *A. strigillosa*), etc. Pre-breeding is increasing world-wide now due to limitations of desirable genes and rising problems of crop losses. Technological advances in genomics are expanding the current and future use of CWR.